

Treatment of Nature in the Works of Toru Dutt**Dr. Pankaj Kumar Prasad**M. A, Ph. D (English)
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Apart from several other things what matters most in the poetry of Toru Dutt is her close association with nature which reminds us of the great doyens of Romantic School of Poetry especially William Wordsworth and John Keats. A close textual analysis of her various poems shows that she has mostly dwelt upon the theme of natural scenes and sights. Like William Wordsworth she also seems to have an innate sense of close conformity with nature. H.M Prasad rightly said;

“Toru Dutt articulates a moral vision through the Indian myths which gives beauty to Human Life. The poems are essentially romantic in treatment of themes and the profusion of Lyricism links her to Wordsworth and Coleridge. Her poetry is sensuous and like Keats, she combines beauty and truth” (P. 04).

Her unflinching love of nature is revealed in her numerous letters in which she expresses her passion for flowers, birds, gardens, fruits and trees. Her letters are full of references to her garden house and beautiful garden, its blooming flowers and sweetening fruits and chirping birds;

“I wish I could send you a basket of fruits of the season.

It would gladden your eyes;

*Yellow or vermillion mangoes, red leeches, white jumrools,
and deep violet jams.” (www.indoangelianpoetry.in)*

Toru Dutt excels in the art of portraying the vivid picture to the minute observation of nature which often ring the note of Romantic euphoria, dream and fantasy. In this connection she seems to be the very close of sensuousness of John Keats and the music and melody of Coleridge and Shelley. Her poem ‘Baugmaree’ which is in the form of Indian sonnet deals

with a rich variety of beauty and delicacy and ease. It has a very simple form and content. The words are very demotic and epigrammatic which call for the simplicity of the poetic diction of Wordsworth. In the very beginning of the poem Baugmaree, the poetess presents a colourful picture of nature:

*A sea of foliage girts our garden round,
But not a sea of dull unvaried green,
Sharp contrasts of all colours here are seen;
The light green graceful tamarinds are abound
Amid the mango clumps of green profound (P. 13)*

Here the colourful portrayal of nature is so beautiful that a sensitive reader is bound to be overwhelmed with the various colours of nature. The alliteration in the lines is also remarkable, jump rhythm shows the jolly and jocund mood of the poet as well as nature. In the poems of Toru Dutt about nature, she expresses her romantic feelings for nature in its Indian settings. In other words we may call her first significant Indo-Anglian nature poet. Beautiful and poetic description of nature cover a large space of “*ballads*”. Her poems of nature contains a complete description of trees, rivers, flowers, gardens, fields, forests, woods, hills brooks and the like. The two forest scenes in “*Savitri*”, the sunset scene in “*Sindhu*”, the description of the different trees and flowers in “*Buttoo*”, the hermitage scene in Sita etc, are remarkable for the description of nature. In comparison of Toru Dutt and Sarojini Naidu as nature poets, Padmini Sen Gupta says, “Observation of nature of the two writers are different. Toru’s description of trees for instance are quite the opposite of Sarojini’s who seems always to feel, maybe due to gose’s advice that all she described must be Indian. To Toru the trees just happened to be Indian which she loves.” Toru said :

*“But nothing can be lovelier than the range
Of bamboos to the east word when the moon
Look through their gaps and white lotus changes
Into a cup of silver. One might swoon
Drunken with beauty then, or gaze and gaze
On primeval Eden, in amaze.” (Baugmaree P. 13)*

In many of Toru's poems nature has been portrayed quite beneficial to mankind, for example when Satyavan and Savitri go to the forest on the fateful day of Satyavan's death, the forest seems to be very beautiful and it seems that all objects of nature were welcoming the couple for this event. Toru Dutt have shown Nature with human like eagerness and welcoming tone of joy in the following lines:

*“Oh! Lovely are the woods at dawn,
And lovely is the sultry noon,
But loveliest, when the sun withdraws
The twilight and a crescent moon
Change all asperities of shape.” (P. 21)*

In the above lines, the poetess describes the charming scene of the forest, beautiful sunset and the new moon. The lines are the proof of sensuousness of the poetess. The colour of the sunset and the sight of the new moon are presented here. The forests are full of palatable smells, the flowers and the birds are also spreading their fragrance. This shows that Toru's poems are full of minute descriptions of nature. She is extremely sensitive to profuse colours of nature. If she has lived longer she would have been great landscape painter just as Keats and Wordsworth are in England. In a small poetic journey of her life, she has been called as the “Keats of India”. Toru Dutt's poetry is remarkable for exceptional sweetness with touching rhythms. It is true that we do not find metrical accomplishment in her poetry, as we find in Naidu's poetry, yet her poems are full of deep sympathy. She has managed octosyllabic lines with great cleverness and skill. The poem “Our Casuarina Tree” is a great example of Toru's technical achievement, as exemplified her:

*Like a huge Python, winding round and round
The rugged trunk indented deep with scars,
Up to its very summit near the stars,
A creeper climbs in whose embraces bound
No other tree could live. But gallantly*

The giant wears the scarfs, and flowers are hung

In crimson clusters all the boughs among

As one of the best examples of nature poetry, the poem takes us that to the world of Coleridge and Wordsworth, Keats and Shelle. Here, poetry is tinged with dream, music, rhythm and above all essence of loneliness and melancholia. The poetry is very powerfully projected, while its lucid diction and phrases make us forget for a while in the simple innocent and ignorant world of romance. In an age of imperialism, Toru had the courage to strike a notice of socialism and democracy with the moral energy of Mahatma Gandhi. Like a true genius, she reduces the fragments of the empty social beliefs and political concepts.

What is rank or caste

In us is honour or disgrace Not our is us... (P.

114)

Like Sarojini Naidu she was an ardent lover of liberty as it is evident from her poems. Toru also draws attention to the fact that in ancient India women enjoyed a status of equality with men. In Savitri:

In those far-off primeval days

Fair India's daughters were not spent In closed Zenanas.

(P. 38)

Toru Dutt has seen and lived nature from close quaters as she takes us to that almost Keatsian world where beauty and truth become each others revelation. She can render the sensuous aspect of sense or a situation with a kind of studied allegiance and economy. The apparent richness is achieved through a judicious interplay of sights, sound and colours. The description of a dark, silent night, in the following lines of "Savitri" leaves a permanent impression in our mind:

*"Under the faint beams of the star,
How beautiful appeared the flowers*

Trees on their path cast a dense shade,

And Nightingale sang mystic rhymes." (P. 50)

Toru also sees divine glory in nature. In “The Tree of life”, she presents a mystic vision, not in sleep, but in a state of wakefulness. It is the vision of her strange tree and light that spreads over a vast plain. So far as the treatment of nature in the poetry of Toru Dutt is concerned, it is often associated with a rich and profound literary style which is very close to the great nature poets of the Romantic age. Most of the poets whose poems Toru has translated belong to the Romantic Movement in French poetry, and Mille Bader tributes her fascination for romantic poetry to her Indian background. She adds that Toru Dutt found in the poets of her choice, “The life-like and dramatic reproduction of the sentiments of heart as well as warmth of imagery and colour”. In this volume, besides this playing a profound knowledge of English and French, Toru shows rare ability and promise of great achievement. It has been noted that Toru was intensely conscious about language and had an effective use of it in her poetry. At that time English was a difficult language and one had to struggle hard with sentences and construction but to Toru, it comes as naturally as leaves come to trees; and she uses its rhythms and diction with perfect skill and control. In the words of Sri Aurobindo, “She was an accomplished verse builder with a delicate talent and some outbreaks of genius and she wrote things that were attractive and something that had a strong energy of language and rhythmic force.” E.F. Oaten appreciates Toru’s “real creative and imaginative power” and her almost faultless technical skills. Toru’s craftsmanship in verse is beautifully brought out in Ancient Ballads and Legends of Hindustan. Toru has to her credit in several of her poems which deals with nature and the beautiful objects of nature. Her language has a special charm of simplicity, melodiousness and spontaneity which reminds us of the poet’s of Romantic School of Poetry.

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